

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report describes the impact of model resolution on dust emission and transport and highlights examples for which dust modeling particularly benefits from storm-resolving model resolutions.

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WP5

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1 Executive summary

Aerosols are an integral part of the Earth system and contribute significantly to the Earth's changing energy budget. Mineral dust dominates the global aerosol mass with a contribution of more than two-thirds (Kinne et al., 2006). Key parameters to quantify dust emission are surface wind intensity and land-surface properties, such as surface roughness or soil texture. Hence, the accuracy at which both are described in models strongly influences that of the modeled dust patterns. Here we demonstrate how the modeling of dust, one of the most important types of atmospheric aerosol, benefits from storm-resolving model resolutions. We further illustrate how storm-resolving dust modeling opens avenues for a more detailed characterization of dust phenomena.

2 Conclusion & Results

We coupled two state-of-the-art physics-based dust emission schemes to the simplified aerosol module HAM-lite (Deliverable 22 [Del. Rel. No. D4.2]) in ICON. Using this model framework, termed ICON-HAM-lite-dust, we conducted a set of sensitivity experiments (EXP1 – EXP8) at a coarse resolution of 80 km to test different dust emission configurations with those two schemes against a reference simulation. Additionally, we conducted one experiment at a high resolution of 5 km (EXP4SR) with the same configuration as our coarse resolution experiment EXP4. With EXP4SR, we demonstrated the benefits of storm-resolving Earth system models for dust generation and transport exemplarily for (a) an area with strong topographical variation, (b) dust storms generated by the outflow from moist convection (haboobs), and (c) a continental-scale dust storm. In all three cases, we see great advances of the greater detail at storm-resolving resolutions for dust modeling, which we summarize in the following.

Surface friction velocity, a key input parameter for dust modeling, shows much more realistic and spatially variable patterns in areas of pronounced topographical variations, for example the Taklamakan desert, a well-known dust source north of the Tibetan plateau. Our experiments show that the locations of areas with high dust optical depth (DOD) differ considerably between resolutions. Climatological reference data based on satellite observations and model reanalysis (with assimilated satellite data) show stronger support for the results we obtain at our storm-resolving resolution of approximately 5 km (experiment EXP4SR) than for the coarser resolution experiment with the same configuration (EXP4).

We developed an algorithm able to identify and track haboobs – severe dust storms generated by the cold pool outflow from moist convection – based on modeled temperature, vertical wind speed, and surface dust concentration. Using this algorithm, we showed that haboobs frequently occur in the storm-resolving simulation (EXP4SR), but, as expected, not at a coarse resolution (EXP4). The reason for this is the much more detailed representation of small-scale variability in meteorological parameters, such as winds and temperature. Storm-resolving modeling, together with our haboob tracking algorithm, allows for the first time to quantify and characterize haboobs globally in a consistent way. An equally consistent characterization is not possible from observations, because clouds interfere with dust detection in satellite data, particularly in the

area of haboobs/thunderstorms, and the spatial coverage of in situ observations is too sparse to detect all haboobs.

In EXP4SR, we identified a massive continental-scale dust storm, comparable to the Godzilla dust storm occurring in June 2020. Similar to the latter, our analyses have shown that haboobs contributed significantly to the development of this storm. We also see from our results that dust outbreaks were often intense, but small in extent. This spatial heterogeneity is hidden at coarser resolutions.

As the next step, we plan to conduct a more detailed evaluation of the average (e.g. monthly or seasonal) spatiotemporal variability of dust patterns against observations (e.g. DOD) to find the best working combination of dust emission scheme, drag partition and soil moisture corrections, and tuning parameters. We also plan to investigate possibilities for reductions of the computational costs of the newly implemented schemes. Once finalized, our developments in ICON-HAM-lite-dust will be included in and be available through ICON-HAM-lite.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	yes
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|---|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
|---|----|

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP5	Relevance in this deliverable?
To test hypotheses, and quantify processes related to aerosols, clouds and their influences on climate change with a new degree of precision and fidelity. (O1 and O2)	yes
To develop parametrisations of cloud micro-physics and mixing, and apply advanced data-assimilation methods to model tuning. (O1)	no
To advance science and support efforts to operationalise the Paris agreement to limit global warming, through improved assessments of aerosol forcing, radiative feedbacks and climate sensitivity. (O2)	yes
To exploit the online diagnostics implemented in the Development phase to investigate the impact of a changing climate on solar and wind energy production in a joint hackathon. (O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

The contribution of aerosols to the Earth's changing energy budget is still subject to considerable uncertainty (e.g. Szopa et al., 2021). The emission of mineral dust, a dominant aerosol type in terms of global mass, is a threshold process that depends non-linearly upon surface wind intensity, which means that the accuracy at which models represent surface winds, together with land-surface properties, is key to estimating dust emissions. For example, haboobs – severe dust storms produced by mesoscale downdrafts from moist-convective systems – are among the most important meteorological dust uplifting processes in the Sahara and Sahel in summer, both in terms of cumulative duration and intensity. However, they cannot be represented at resolutions coarser than a few kilometers. Our goals for this deliverable were therefore to take advantage of the explicitly simulated wind gusts in single-digit kilometer resolution ICON simulations, in combination with existing physically-based parameterizations of the dust emission process, along with a more detailed representation of dust-relevant land-surface properties at high resolution. We explicitly wanted to avoid commonly used empirical constraints upon source location and emission strength to allow dust emissions to dynamically respond to a changing climate. Based on this framework, we aimed to demonstrate the benefit of high resolution for the modeling of dust emission and transport, e.g. for a continental-scale dust storm in which moist convection plays an important role for dust generation. For this purpose, we conducted simulations at resolutions of (a) approximately 80 km to test new model developments, and (b) 5 km to investigate the impact of storm-resolving resolutions on dust modeling.

4.1 Implementation of two state-of-the-art physics-based dust emission parameterizations

Two state-of-the-art physics-based dust emission parameterization schemes were implemented in ICON using the simplified aerosol module HAM-lite (see Deliverable 22 [Del. Rel. No. D4.2]) as the framework. The two schemes are those from Shao (2004) and Kok et al. (2014), which we refer to as S04 and K14, respectively, in the following. Both schemes have been extensively tested and evaluated at coarse resolution (Klose et al., 2021). The S04 scheme has also been tested at a storm-resolving resolution (~ 3 km) for a regional domain (Unser et al., 2024, in prep.). The implementation of both schemes in ICON follows largely that described in Klose et al. (2021) for the MONARCH model. The implementation is briefly summarized in the following. In this report, we refer to the new model version as ICON-HAM-lite-dust.

The S04 scheme estimates size-resolved dust emission based on the soil volume removed by impacting saltation particles, i.e. sand-sized soil particles or particle aggregates that hop along the surface due to wind forces. The scheme requires information about the particle size distributions (PSDs) of the parent soil for each soil texture class, analyzed both after minimal and full dispersion. Here, we determine the soil texture class based on the fractions of sand, silt, and clay from the Harmonized World Soil Database (HWSD) (Food and United Nations, n.d.) using the soil texture triangle of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). The parent soil PSDs are then calculated as the sum of four log-normal distributions, the parameters for which were obtained from soil samples and are fixed (Klose et al., 2021).

The K14 scheme describes the amount and size distribution of emitted dust as analogue to the fragmentation of brittle material. It requires information on the soil clay fraction, which we directly define as a boundary condition.

In both schemes, dust is emitted as soon as the friction velocity, u_* , exceeds a threshold value, i.e. the threshold friction velocity, u_{*t} . The friction velocity is calculated based on the law of the wall (logarithmic wind profile):

$$u_* = \kappa u \ln(z_0/z) \quad (1)$$

with von Karman constant $\kappa = 0.4$, surface wind speed u , aerodynamic roughness length z_0 , and height $z = 10$ m, analogue to HAM (Stier et al., 2005; Tegen et al., 2019; Salzmann et al., 2022). The aerodynamic roughness length z_0 is determined as described in Klose et al. (2021) using a combination of a static roughness length specifically suitable for desert surfaces (Prigent et al., 2012) and a dynamic roughness length based on leaf area index (LAI) and vegetation cover fraction. For the latter, either LAI and vegetation fraction from JSBACH can be used (referred to as vegetation option VEG0), or newly implemented data using monthly climatological (for years 2001–2017) photosynthetic and nonphotosynthetic vegetation cover fractions (Guerschman et al., 2015), interpolated to the day of simulation (vegetation option VEG1). To determine the shear stress at the surface available for dust uplift, a drag partitioning is applied, which accounts for drag on roughness elements, such as vegetation, that reduces the drag acting on the surface and causing dust emission. For this purpose, the drag partition parameterizations from Raupach et al. (1993) (DPR) and Marticorena and Bergametti (1995) (DPM) were implemented. The former utilizes the dynamic photosynthetic and near-static nonphotosynthetic vegetation cover data sets from Guerschman et al. (2015), whereas the latter deploys the aerodynamic roughness length z_0 as described before together with a corresponding roughness length of the bare soil. The drag partitioning results in a correction factor, f_v , to u_* between 0 and 1. In desert areas with little roughness, the correction factor is close to 1 such that soil friction velocities $u_{*,dust}$ are maximal and approximately equal to u_* . In vegetated areas, f_v is small which minimizes $u_{*,dust}$ and hence prevents dust emission. Both drag partition parameterizations can be selected in combination with each of the two new dust emission schemes.

The threshold friction velocity, u_{*t} , is calculated based on Shao and Lu (2000). As soil water increases cohesion between soil particles, u_{*t} is also increased. This effect is accounted for through a soil moisture correction factor to u_{*t} . This correction factor can be estimated either following Fécan et al. (1999) or Klose et al. (2014). Both approaches use soil moisture from JSBACH as an input. Additionally, a scaling factor, c_t , between 0 and 1 can be applied to u_{*t} . This factor can be used to lower u_{*t} globally in a uniform way if otherwise emissions occur from a too small area. This can occur, e.g. due to differences between the particle-scale value of u_{*t} and the grid-scale value of u_* .

To describe areas from which dust emission is possible (i.e. precluding water surfaces, bedrock, etc.), we utilize the climatological (for years 2003–2015) frequency of occurrence (FoO) of the MODIS Deep Blue dust optical depth (DOD) greater than 0.2 (Hsu et al., 2004; Ginoux et al., 2012). For a given location, dust can be emitted if FoO(DOD>0.2) is greater than 0.025 (Klose et al., 2021). Most importantly, the FoO is not used to regulate the dust emission flux, but only to define potential dust source areas.

The newly implemented land-surface data are all available at relatively high spatial resolution

Table 3: Configurations of the sensitivity experiments carried out to test the performance of the implemented dust emission schemes, together with the used computing time. All experiments used $c_t = 0.6$ and the soil moisture correction from Klose et al. (2014). The HAM dust emission scheme is described in Tegen et al. (2019). Simulations of approximately one-month length were conducted for February, March, April, June, July, and August, and initialized with ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2017; Simmons et al., 2020; Muñoz-Sabater, 2020).

Experiment name	Dust emission scheme	Drag partition	Vegetation option	Node hours per simulation day
REF	HAM			0.323
EXP1	S04	DPR	VEG0	0.407
EXP2	S04	DPR	VEG1	0.353
EXP3	S04	DPM	VEG0	0.387
EXP4	S04	DPM	VEG1	0.373
EXP5	K14	DPR	VEG0	0.308
EXP6	K14	DPR	VEG1	0.308
EXP7	K14	DPM	VEG0	0.308
EXP8	K14	DPM	VEG1	0.307

(static aerodynamic roughness length and MODIS FoO at 0.1° , photosynthetic/non-photosynthetic vegetation cover fractions at 0.05°). This allows a much more detailed estimation of dust emission than from areal averaged data.

4.1.1 Preliminary evaluation of the two parameterizations

A set of sensitivity experiments was conducted using ICON-HAM-lite-dust at an initial resolution of R2B5 (approximately 80 km) to test and compare the newly implemented schemes. The configurations used in each run are listed in Tab. 3. Model runs for one year were planned to analyze the annual dust cycle obtained with the three schemes (S04, K14, and the default scheme already implemented in HAM/HAM-lite (Tegen et al., 2019)), however, technical issues occurring with all three schemes and at different resolutions did not allow finalizing the full annual runs. This issue is still being investigated. Our initial assessment is therefore based on shorter-term simulations to obtain estimates for February, March, April, June, July, and August.

To calibrate the new schemes, we used results of the default HAM dust scheme. A global calibration factor was derived comparing the monthly global dust emissions obtained with a given configuration (Fig. 1) to that obtained with the default HAM scheme (Tegen et al., 2019). These calibration factors neither affect the spatial distribution nor the temporal variability of the dust

Figure 1: Monthly global average dust emissions obtained for the sensitivity experiments listed in Table 3 and used for calibration of the dust fields.

patterns, but only the overall magnitude. This means that the spatiotemporal patterns produced by a dust emission scheme are not affected and can still be evaluated to assess its performance. In our tests, the calibration factor was applied consistently to all dust fields (emission, deposition, optical depth, column loading) a posteriori. A more detailed calibration against observed dust optical depth will be conducted later on. The so obtained final calibration factor will later be implemented in ICON-HAM-lite-dust and applied a priori to dust emissions online (which will then translate to the other dust fields). With the exception of EXP6, all schemes display a peak in monthly global dust emissions in March and April. EXP6 produces relatively similar monthly dust emission fluxes between January and August. The HAM emission scheme yields dust emissions in August that are even greater than those in March.

Figures 2 and 3 show, respectively, global column dust loading and dust optical depth (DOD) during June, July, and August for the nine experiments. In all schemes, the highest dust load and DOD occurred in western North Africa, consistent with currently available dust constraints (Kok et al., 2021). Generally, regions with high dust loading or DOD in experiments with the K14 scheme are more widespread in northern Africa compared to those with the S04 scheme and also with the default HAM scheme. All experiments also show emissions from Australia, southern Africa, South America, and North America, but the contributions from those regions vary between experiments, primarily with the drag partition option. This is expected as those regions are partly vegetated and are therefore sensitive to the description of the impact of vegetation roughness on dust emission. The configuration used in EXP5 and EXP8 (DPR and VEG1) is most permissive in this sense, i.e. dust emissions are not reduced as strongly in vegetated areas as with other drag partition and vegetation options (DPM and VEG0). Overall, all experiments produce patterns of dust loading and DOD that are largely consistent with those obtained with the HAM reference simulation, but the contributions from individual source regions differ between experiments. A more in-depth evaluation against observations will guide the choice

Figure 2: Average column dust loading (burden) during June, July, and August obtained for the sensitivity experiments listed in Table 3 (calibration factor applied).

Figure 3: Average dust optical depth during June, July, and August obtained for the sensitivity experiments listed in Table 3 (calibration factor applied).

of an optimal configuration. Most notably, the HAM scheme deploys region-dependent scaling factors to achieve globally well-balanced dust fields close to a reference, whereas the newly implemented schemes only use a single global calibration factor. Their spatiotemporal balance depends solely on the used land-surface description, besides the atmospheric forcing which is the same in all experiments.

For storm-resolving model applications, the computational cost is particularly important. For that reason, we evaluated the computing time needed per day of simulation for our experiments (Tab. 3). The computational cost of the newly implemented schemes are comparable to those used in REF. Experiments using the K14 dust emission scheme needed slightly less resources, whereas those using the S04 scheme needed slightly more. We plan to investigate whether the computational efficiency of the new configurations can be further reduced.

4.2 Benefits of single-digit kilometer resolutions for dust modeling

In the following, we describe the benefits of the storm-resolving model resolutions used in nextGEMS for dust modeling for three aspects: (i) impact of topography, (ii) haboob dust storms, and (iii) an example case of a continental-scale dust storm. For this purpose, we repeated EXP4 in Tab. 3 (resolution R2B5, i.e. about 80 km) at a resolution of R2B9 (approximately 5 km) for June 2020 and refer to this experiment as EXP4SR. EXP4SR was also initialized with ERA5 reanalyses (see Tab. 3). The first 10 days of the simulation were used for model spin up and were discarded from the analyses.

4.2.1 Impact of topography on dust emission

Topographic features act as a barrier to the atmospheric flow and therefore have a strong impact on modeled wind speeds. At coarser resolutions, topographic height is averaged over a larger area, leading to a smoother surface and lower mountain tops. As wind friction at the surface is a driving factor for dust emissions, changes in topography-related winds are expected to impact dust patterns.

A known prolific dust source with pronounced topography in its surrounding is the Taklamakan desert, located in the Tarim basin in Asia. The Tarim basin is relatively open toward the East, but surrounded by the Tian Shan, Parim, and Kunlun Shan (the northern edge of the Tibetan plateau) mountain ranges toward the North, West, and South. Fig. 4a,c show topographic height for this area at resolutions of approximately 5 km (R2B9) and 80 km (R2B5). Noteworthy is especially the better representation of smaller-scale topographic features in the northeastern part of the Tarim basin (best visible in Fig. 4b,d from the 1750 m topographic height contour line), which are largely absent at 80 km resolution. Surface friction velocities are particularly pronounced in those valleys at 5 km resolution (Fig. 4b). At 80 km resolution, friction velocities are generally much lower and variability in the aforementioned area is lacking due to the missing topographic features (Fig. 4d). Fig. 4 also shows DOD from EXP4SR and EXP4 as well as from the MIDAS data set (Gkikas et al., 2021), which combines daily aerosol optical depth (AOD) from MODIS-Aqua with modeled DOD-to-AOD ratios from MERRA-2 (Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for

Figure 4: (a, c) Topographic height (shading) and monthly mean DOD from our simulations for June 2020 (colored contour lines) and the climatological mean (years 2003 - 2017) for June from MIDAS (Gkikas et al., 2021, black contour line), and (b, d) monthly (June) mean surface friction velocity from EXP4SR (a, b) and EXP4 (c, d) for the Taklamakan desert and part of the Tibetan plateau in Asia. The gray contour in (b, d) indicates the 1750 m topographic height level.

Research and Applications version 2) reanalyses to obtain DOD at a resolution of 0.1° . In EXP4, there is only a single area of elevated DOD within the Tarim basin in the south of the Taklamakan desert. In contrast, high DOD in EXP4SR is mainly in the eastern part of the Taklamakan desert and much more spatially variable. A part of this area coincides with an area of increased DOD from MIDAS, however the latter shows additional areas toward the southern/southeastern edge of the Taklamakan desert, contrary to both EXP4 and EXP4SR. It is important to note that (1) the DOD from MIDAS is a multiyear climatology, which may vary between individual years, (2) DOD-to-AOD ratios in MIDAS are model based and may also include model errors, and (3) the resolution of the MERRA-2 reanalysis data, which is used in MIDAS to convert AOD to DOD, is $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$, which is between EXP4SR and EXP4, but closer to the latter. This may explain a southwestward displacement between MIDAS and EXP4SR, but would need to be confirmed by a more detailed analysis. Overall, the MIDAS data support both location and spatial variability of DOD for EXP4SR more than for EXP4.

4.2.2 Haboob dust storms

To be able to identify and characterize haboob dust storms from the storm-resolving simulations, a haboob tracking algorithm has been developed (Unser et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025, both in prep.). The haboob leading edge grids are detected based on three criteria: (1) temperature tendency anomaly (compared to a five day average) at 925 hPa less than -0.05 K min^{-1} ; (2) absolute value of vertical velocity at 850 hPa exceeding 0.5 m s^{-1} ; (3) normalized surface dust

concentration tendency greater than 0.05 min^{-1} . The so identified haboob leading edge points are then connected spatially using the DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with noise) algorithm. The resulting haboob point clusters are subsequently connected in time using a distance criterion for which we estimated how far a haboob may travel between two subsequent model output time steps (here 10 km within 15 min). This allows identifying and tracking a haboob during its lifetime. Finally, haboobs that are short-lived (lasting less than one hour) or remain stationary over the topographical and coastal regions are filtered out.

The threshold values applied in each of the three criteria mentioned in the previous paragraph were chosen for a resolution of R2B9 as used in EXP4SR. As the intensities of temperature anomalies, vertical wind velocity, and dust concentration tendency depend on resolution, the exact values chosen as thresholds need to be adjusted as well. We did not expect any haboobs to occur at a resolution of R2B5, however, to confirm this presumption, we have applied the haboob tracking algorithm also to EXP4, but with substantially relaxed criteria of (a) $-0.015 \text{ K min}^{-1}$, (b) 0.04 m s^{-1} , and (c) 0.004 min^{-1} .

Figure 5 shows surface dust concentration and topography for northern Africa and North America for EXP4 (80 km) and EXP4SR (5 km), together with the haboobs identified by our tracking algorithm. Several haboobs were identified in EXP4SR in northern Africa and a few in North America (Figs. 5a,b), whereas - as expected - none were found in EXP4 in either region (Figs. 5c,d). In EXP4SR, haboobs contributed considerably to surface dust concentrations. In EXP4, surface dust concentrations were widespread and intense, despite the lack of haboob dust storms. It is important to note that we calibrated monthly global dust emissions in EXP4 against REF, whereas we did not for EXP4SR due to the different resolution. A more detailed calibration against observations as well as a sensitivity study to optimize the selection of parameterizations and parameters is planned as a next step (see Sec. 2). The magnitude of surface dust concentrations may therefore be systematically biased between the two experiments.

That storm-resolving resolutions, such as R2B9 as used in EXP4SR, yield a much more detailed picture of atmospheric winds and are better able to reproduce the tail of the wind speed probability distribution, a circumstance highly beneficial for dust modeling, is demonstrated in Fig. 6. There we show 10 m wind speed for EXP4 and EXP4SR. In both simulations, wind speeds in the range up to about 10 m s^{-1} are prevalent in most areas. Higher wind speeds are only present in EXP4SR (Fig. 6a), at a few locations, often those of haboobs (Figs. 5a). As dust emission is a threshold process, those locations are most relevant for dust emissions. The reason why considerable amounts of dust are present in EXP4 nevertheless is likely the parameter c_t , the purpose of which is exactly to allow for dust emissions even at coarse resolutions where wind shears are smaller. The planned sensitivity experiments will be used to optimize the value of c_t to improve the spatial dust patterns and increase the benefit of a more nuanced atmospheric flow field even more.

4.2.3 Continental-scale dust storm: The Godzilla dust storm in June 2020

Between 13th and 27th June, a massive dust storm developed in northern Africa, was transported across the Atlantic ocean and reached North America (Fig. 7). In media reports it was termed the "Godzilla dust storm" due to its exceptional extent and intensity. Yu et al. (2021)

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of surface dust concentration and topographic height for (a, c) northern Africa at 19:00 on June 27 and (b, d) North America at 01:00 on June 20. (a, b) show results at 5 km while (c, d) are for 80 km. Colored dots represent identified haboob leading edge points, with different colors representing different clusters (i.e. different haboobs). Note that dust concentration in EXP4 was calibrated against REF, whereas EXP4SR was not.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of 10 m wind speed over Northern Africa at 19:00 on June 27 for (a) 5 km and (b) 80 km simulations.

Figure 7: Visualization of the "Godzilla dust storm" based on near real-time VIIRS Corrected Reflectance (True Color) daily imagery for 18th June 2020. Image credit: NASA's Scientific Visualization Studio. They acknowledge the use of imagery provided by services from NASA's Global Imagery Browse Services (GIBS), part of NASA's Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS).

found that haboobs contributed significantly to the dust storm and were a reason why their model did not capture its full intensity. Inspired by this outstanding dust event, we chose June 2020 for EXP4SR to see if a possible development of a continental-scale dust storm, such as the Godzilla dust storm - benefits from the presence of haboobs in the simulation. Note that, after initialization with ERA5 (see Sec. 4.2), EXP4SR was conducted as a free run such that we do not expect to be able to reproduce the Godzilla dust event exactly.

Indeed, a continental-scale dust storm occurred in EXP4SR (Fig. 8), but dust transport across the Atlantic occurred later than in reality. The dust storm was caused by a series of intense dust events. Initially, repeated dust outbreaks in southeastern North Africa (initially Sudan, later also Chad) starting from 12th June (not shown) led to an increase in DOD over southern North Africa. Starting from 18th June, severe dust emissions from Mali lead to very high DOD and from 21st June until the end of our simulation (end of June), most of southwestern North Africa experienced repeated dust outbreaks, forming a well-developed dust plume across the Atlantic. Dust outbreaks from eastern North Africa continued to occur during large parts of the period. Fig. 8 shows the evolution of DOD between 24th and 30th June 2020. Clearly visible are the very high DOD in Mali (especially Fig. 8b,d), dust outbreaks across large parts of southwestern (Fig. 8a) and southeastern (Fig. 8c,d) North Africa. Fig. 8 also showcases the intense dust plume meandering across the Atlantic ocean and progressing toward North America.

Corresponding to the DOD shown in Fig. 8a, Fig. 8e shows surface dust concentrations together with the identified haboob clusters. Our analysis demonstrates that several of the dust plumes are associated with haboobs. Interestingly, the most intense dust outbreak at around 0°E and 15°N is only partly identified as a haboob, because at some locations some of the identification criteria are not met. As the choice of the threshold values remains to some extent arbitrary, it may be that a slight relaxation of the threshold values would lead to a wider extending haboob, covering the region associated with the strongest DOD. However, a more detailed analysis would be needed to confirm whether this dust outbreak was indeed due to a haboob or not.

Figure 8: Temporal evolution of a continental-scale dust storm occurring over northern Africa and the Atlantic ocean in EXP4SR: dust optical depth (DOD) on (a) 24th June 2020 22 UTC, (b) 27th June 2020 19 UTC, (c) 29th June 2020 00 UTC, and (d) 30th June 2020 16 UTC; and (e) surface dust concentration (red shading) and identified haboob clusters (dots) over northern Africa for 24th June 2020 22 UTC (same time as in a), together with surface topography (gray shading).

5 References (Bibliography)

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>).

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

Delayed by two months compared to the original deadline (31st August 2024). An extension of the deadline to 30th September 2024 was granted by the PO.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable is closely linked with work package 4.2 ("Introducing aerosol with reduced complexity model") and the corresponding Deliverable 22 [Del. Rel. No. D4.2] ("Report on implementation and evaluation of simplified aerosol model"), work package 4.3 ("Producing dust emissions in support of aerosol module"), and work package 5.6 ("Dust generation and transport in continental-scale dust storm").

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna

- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024
- "4th km-scale hackathon" (First nextGEMS application phase hackathon); 04. – 08. March 2024 in Hamburg
- Social Media: https://fediscience.org/@nextgems_eu, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nextgems-eu-horizon2020>

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>